

Influence of Acidity of Gelatine on the Liesegang Rings of Silver Chromate and Silver Iodide.

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Desai and Nabar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 141) have studied the changes in the nature of rings of silver chromate in gelatine when the acidity of the latter is increased. They have observed that an increase in the acidity of gelatine is accompanied by a decrease (i) in the time after which the first ring appears, (ii) in the distance between the same successive rings, and (iii) in the number of rings that can be obtained. While discussing their results they have suggested that there might be definite limits to the p_H value of gelatine within which good rings of silver chromate can be obtained. The present work was undertaken with a view to test this suggestion by obtaining rings of silver chromate in gelatine whose p_H is varied over a wide range and also to see if the variation of p_H has any influence on the nature of rings of silver iodide in gelatine. The sample of gelatine used in these experiments was the same as used by Desai and Naik (Paper on "Inhibitive power of gelatine" which will be published in the September issue of the *Journal of the Bombay University*, 1933) and the p_H of gelatine solution was varied in the same manner as done by them.

Rings of Silver Chromate in Gelatine.

1.5 C.c. of a normal solution of silver nitrate were allowed to diffuse into 20 c. c. of a 20 % gelatine gel impregnated with 0.9 c.c. of a normal solution of potassium chromate. The test tubes used in these experiments were all of the same diameter. The experiments were carried out in a room whose temperature (30°) did not appreciably fluctuate during the day. The distances between successive rings were measured by means of a cathetometer. The results are summarised below.

(1) Maximum number of rings are obtained with samples of gelatine having p_H 5.25 and 5.00 and their number decreases in gels of higher or lower p_H than this range.

(2) The distances between successive rings increase with all samples of gelatine. The distances between the same successive rings are greatest for gelatine of p_H 5.75 and smaller for samples of gelatine of p_H higher or lower than 5.75.

(3) Rings appear early in acidified gelatine while their appearance is delayed in samples whose acidity has been decreased. In conformity with this, the distance of the first ring from the top increases with an increase of p_H .

The following observations were also made during this work.

(4) There is a tendency to get spiral shaped or broken rings in samples of acidified gelatine and larger and larger crystals are obtained with an increase of acidity. In samples of gelatine whose p_H is high, no rings are obtained and the precipitate is found to be more or less uniformly distributed.

(5) The size of the particles in the rings generally increases from the first to the last ring.

In Fig. 1 is given a photograph of rings of silver chromate in samples of gelatine of different p_H . This photograph was taken with transmitted light. It corroborates what has been stated above. In test tube No. 1, one can easily see the presence

of big crystals. The following additional conclusions can be drawn from the photograph.

(6) With an increase in the acidity of gelatine the thickness of the rings decreases.

(7) In any particular sample of gelatine, the thickness of the rings increases from the first ring to the last ring, but its compactness decreases at the same time.

These results support largely the observations of Desai and Nabar (*loc. cit.*). The slight differences in the results are due to changes in the concentration of gelatine and the reactants used in their experiments and in the present investigation. The influence of these factors is being further studied in greater detail.

The present results, however, completely support the suggestion of Desai and Nabar (*loc. cit.*) that there might be a definite range of p_H of gelatine within which good rings of silver chromate can be obtained.

It has been shown by us (Naik, Desai and Desai, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 45) that the results about condition of silver chromate in gelatine in the yellow mixture are rather conflicting. It might exist either in supersaturated condition, colloidal condition or in a highly dispersed condition—particles being even of molecular size (*cf.* Naik, Desai and Desai, *loc. cit.*), in any two of the three or even simultaneously in all the three conditions. It is therefore considered advisable not to explain these results of ring experiments until we are able to find out the causes of the conflicting nature of the results of different investigators as well as our own different sets of experiments about the condition of silver chromate in the yellow mixture. It should, however, be stated that these experiments clearly show that samples of gelatine which are slightly acidic give good rings of silver chromate while those which may be relatively more alkaline may not give any rings at all. Also there is a definite range of p_H of gelatine in which good rings of silver chromate can be obtained; the fact that gelatine with p_H 5.75 (Desai and Naik, *loc. cit.*) shows a minimum inhibitive power seems to have a bearing on the distances *between the same successive rings* (*cf.* section 2 above). Bolam and Donaldson (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1933, 29, 864) have pointed out that the degree of supersaturation of silver chromate in gelatine increases slightly as the p_H decreases from 5.7 to 5.0, and then falls off more rapidly as

the p_H is further decreased. They have concluded that the degree of supersaturation probably has an optimum value at p_H 5.0. This fact seems to have some bearing on the nature of rings of silver chromate in gelatine, for as shown above best rings are obtained in samples of gelatine of p_H range, 5.0 to 5.25.

Rings of Silver Iodide in Gelatine.

1.5 C.c. of a 20% silver nitrate solution were allowed to diffuse into 20 c.c. of a 20% gelatine gel impregnated with 1 c.c. of a normal solution of potassium iodide. The test tubes were kept in a dark box during the period of formation of rings in order to prevent the effect of light as far as possible. The results of these experiments are summarised below.

(1) All samples of gelatine are equally effective in giving rings of silver iodide. Thirty three rings were obtained in each case.

(2) In all the cases the distances between successive rings first decrease regularly and then increase. The closest rings are those which occur between the eighteenth and the twentythird ring.

(3) The distances between the same successive rings decrease more or less regularly with an increase of the p_H of gelatine.

(4) The first ring appears after about 23 hours in all the cases.

From observation (3) it would appear that for values of p_H much higher than 6.0, only a continuous band of precipitate might be obtained instead of a number of rings. This is rather interesting in view of the fact as shown by Desai and Naik (*loc. cit.*) that the inhibitive power of gelatine with reference to AgI continuously increases with an increase in the p_H of gelatine. It is, however, necessary to carry out more experiments before this fact can be utilised to explain the nature of rings of silver iodide in gelatine.

Silver iodide being relatively very much sensitive to light when compared with silver chromate, it was not found possible to get a good photograph of rings either with transmitted or reflected light. We would however like to record the following visual observations here.

(1) The thickness of the rings is generally much greater than the distance of the clear interspace between the rings.

(2) The thickness of the rings almost regularly decreases from the first ring upto the eighteenth to twentythird ring after which it again begins to increase regularly.

(3) All the rings have got almost the same compactness.

(4) The size of the particles in almost all the rings remains almost the same.

(5) The clear interspace between the first and the eighteenth to twentythird ring became somewhat darkish on exposure to light, while that between the eighteenth to twentythird and the thirtythird ring became deep brown.

According to the various theories that have been put forward to explain the Liesegang phenomena, there should be a gradual increase in the spacing between the successive rings. The fact that the distance between the successive rings of AgI in gelatine decreases up to about the twentieth ring cannot therefore be explained on the basis of any of the existing theories. The other noteworthy instances of this type, *i.e.*, where the distance between the successive rings decreases, are those reported by Davis (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 1312) about bands of mercury obtained by allowing mercurous nitrate to diffuse in agar gel impregnated with sodium formate, by Hedges and Henley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2714) about bands of arsenious sulphide obtained by allowing solutions of ferric chloride or aluminium sulphate to diffuse into agar gel containing sols of arsenious sulphide, and by Mukherjee and Chatterji (*Kolloid Z.*, 1930, 50, 147) about bands of zinc and nickel ferricyanide and cobalt ferrocyanide. The rings of AgI in gelatine obtained by us are, however, peculiar in this respect that although the distance between successive rings first decreases, it increases in case of the later rings (twentieth to twentythird ring). More detailed work is necessary before these anomalies can be explained.

It has been shown by us (Naik, Desai and Desai, *loc. cit.*) that about, 90% of AgI in gelatine exists in the mixture in condition other than ionic or colloidal. The particles of silver iodide which form on the meeting of AgNO_3 and KI are first probably in molecular condition and they grow further due to diffusion. The particles being in a very highly dispersed form, might absorb to a certain extent the substances that may be present in the neighbourhood. However in view of the fact that the space between the rings becomes coloured when exposed to light, it appears that the adsorption may not be very marked.

SUMMARY.

1. Liesegang rings of silver chromate and silver iodide have been obtained in samples of gelatine of different p_H .

2. In the case of silver chromate rings, the results in general support the preliminary results of Desai and Nabar. The suggestion of these authors that there might be a definite range of p_H of gelatine within which good rings of silver chromate can be obtained is also supported by the present results.

3. All samples of gelatine appear to be equally effective in giving rings of silver iodide. The distance between successive rings first decreases and then increases. Also the distances between the same successive rings decrease more or less regularly with an increase of the p_H of gelatine.

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